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Waste heat inconsistencies in the EU's energy legislation

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ABSTRACT

This paper critically examines the legal definition of waste heat and the provisions on waste heat in the European Union's Renewable Energy Directive (RED III). The legal definition is crucial for aligning waste heat with the overarching energy efficiency and renewable energy objectives and has direct implications for the efficient use of energy and national policies. The legal analysis identifies ambiguities and inconsistencies that may result in uncertainty and the non-implementation of waste heat measures. The paper concludes with recommendations to improve the clarity and derive practical applicability of the aforementioned provisions.

1. Introduction

Waste heat is excess energy that is left over after a process. Reusing this energy avoids using other primary energy sources, thus reducing overall energy consumption. The substitution of waste heat for fossil fuels can substantially contribute to the overall process of decarbonization and the specific goal of decarbonizing district heating, as discussed in this paper. If it replaces renewable final energy, the potential of renewable resources can be redirected elsewhere.

Luberti et al. (2022) calculated the potential for waste heat from power plants and industry with a temperature below 100 °C in the European Union to be 2437 TWh. If waste heat at such temperature levels cannot be reused in company-internal processes, Moser and Lassacher (2020) demonstrate that district heating networks represent the optimal sink for such energy. From an alternative standpoint, Siddique et al. (2023) underscore the necessity for waste heat to facilitate the decarbonization of district heating. As a consequence of discrepancies in the profiles of the energy sources in question, the geographical localization of these sources, and the temperature requirements of the district heating networks, the amount of energy that can be used in such networks is significantly lower than might be expected. This situation is explained by Böhm et al. (2021) using the example of waste heat from electrolysis. However, Papapetrou et al. (2018) derive the technically feasible potential from industry in the European Union to be 300 TWh per year.

As Christodoulides et al. (2022) observed, implementing waste heat recovery technologies is constrained by several factors, including a lack

of information and technical expertise, technological risks, and the high initial, operational, and maintenance costs associated with such systems. Additional challenges include inadequate financial support and government incentives, spatial and size limitations, insufficient infrastructure, production constraints and the potential for disruption, adverse effects on business operations, and restrictive policies and regulations.

In particular, if the waste heat is to be reused internally, the primary challenges of recovery and reuse are technical and economic feasibility. In the case of external reuse, other factors, such as trust and asymmetric information, are of primary importance (see Rodin Moser, 2021; Moser and Rodin, 2021). These barriers include initial investment costs, the assessment of market risks, technical hurdles, and risk of failure due to technical defects, maintenance requirements, and risks such as process change, plant relocation, or bankruptcy of the industrial partner (Moser and Jauschnik, 2023). Moreover, Lygnerud et al. (2019) emphasize that urban waste heat recovery is constrained by some substantial limitations, particularly in the non-technical domain. Establishing heat supply contracts between district heating companies and waste heat owners represents a significant challenge, as do the uncertainties inherent in business models tailored to urban waste heat recovery. Furthermore, stakeholders have identified legal, financial, and organizational barriers, including misaligned incentives, the absence of standardized contract templates, and ambiguous risk-sharing arrangements. Furthermore, the lack of collaboration among stakeholders and the absence of a coherent regulatory framework impede the widespread implementation of this technology.

In light of the numerous and interdisciplinary obstacles, risks, and

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uncertainties, particularly in multi-actor scenarios involving industry and district heating operators, it is imperative to at least mitigate the investment uncertainties stemming from regulatory requirements. Moreover, Schmidt et al. (2020, pp. 5-12) have identified significant barriers to urban waste heat recovery, particularly the dependence on district heating networks. In the absence of district heating networks, the parallel deployment of waste heat recovery and the rapid expansion of district heating networks would be required for waste heat recovery to be feasible. Identifying and quantifying waste heat sources is also challenging due to limitations in the availability of data, concerns regarding confidentiality, and the lack of sufficient monitoring equipment. Smaller industries and unconventional sources are frequently excluded from centralized databases, while available data may be imprecise or inaccessible. Moreover, waste heat owners frequently lack the requisite expertise or incentive to supply to district heating networks, as the potential benefits may not outweigh the costs or risks to core operations.

1.1. Context of waste heat in European legislation

In December 2019, the European Commission presented the European Green Deal, which aims to eliminate net greenhouse gas emissions by 2050 (European Commission, 2019a). This policy resulted in the enactment of several EU directives, with the Renewable Energy Directive (RED) being of particular relevance to the interaction between waste heat and district heating. While the topic of waste heat was not a prominent feature of RED II (EU Directive, 2018/2001, see European Union, 2018), it has been given significant attention in RED III (EU Directive, 2023/2413, see European Union, 2023b). This attention represents a notable advancement and a stronger focus on waste heat. The revised version of the Energy Efficiency Directive (EED III, EU Directive, 2023/1791, see European Union, 2023a) also contains intricate regulations on utilizing and assessing waste heat. Nevertheless, it is specified that the legal definition of RED III is the determining factor in the application of its provisions (Recital 105).

RED III asserts that, despite its pervasive availability, waste heat remains underutilized, resulting in a waste of resources, inadequate energy efficiency in national energy systems, and excessively high energy consumption within the Union (Recital 70). In light of these developments, the current versions of RED III and EED III mandate that Member States integrate waste heat into their national decarbonization strategies, subject to certain limitations. Additionally, they require the assessment of potential applications of waste heat, such as the optimization of data center efficiency.

RED III legally defines waste heat as "unavoidable heat [...] generated as a by-product in industrial or electricity-producing installations, or in the tertiary sector, which would be dissipated unused in air or water without access to a district heating [...], where a cogeneration process has been used or will be used or where cogeneration is not feasible" (Article 2(9)). The brackets exclude "waste cold" and "district cooling" for the sake of improved readability.

A review of the technical literature reveals some approaches to classifying and categorizing waste heat. Firstly, it distinguishes between waste heat that can be utilized and waste heat that has been rendered irrecoverable (see the differentiation between resource and reserve in Bendig et al., 2012). The temperature level of the waste heat is an essential parameter; higher temperatures facilitate more diverse and straightforward utilization. Researchers have often classified temperature levels as high, medium, and low. However, the boundaries between the temperature levels vary. Ja'fari et al. (2023) indicate that the thresholds between low/medium and medium/high are 200 and 500 °C, respectively. Forni et al. (2012) concentrate on a range between 200 and 400 °C for utilization with Organic Rankin Cycle (ORC) technology. A concise overview of alternative proposed thresholds is provided by Gangar et al. (2020). However, Ja'fari et al. (2023) indicate that the actual range of observed temperatures is 50 °C–1000 °C or higher.

Ammar et al. (2012) refer to "waste heat" only if the temperature is lower than that of the coldest internal heat sink. In cases where the temperature is higher than that, they define the economic viability of recovery as the determining factor. Low-grade waste heat may only be applied for space heating. In the district heating sector, the distinction between the temperature levels is entirely different: Many district heating systems have "high" forerun temperatures above 100 °C, while "low-temperature" fourth-generation systems have temperatures below 70 °C (Lund et al., 2014). Waste heat recovery at the highest possible temperature level is a key objective, as it allows for the greatest number of potential uses.

In contrast, low-grade waste heat faces several challenges (Böhm et al., 2021; Ammar et al., 2012). Recoverable waste heat may be avoided by implementing appropriate measures, reusing within the process or elsewhere on-site, or providing externally (Ja'fari et al., 2023). The distinction between theoretical, technical, economic, and realizable potentials depends on the nature and occurrence of the waste heat (Larrinaga et al., 2021; Bühler et al., 2018). Oluleye et al. (2015) posit that internal utilization is typically the most economically viable option, given the challenges associated with justifying the economic viability of external utilization through the construction of a heating network.

1.2. Aim of the paper

In light of the legislative package's objective of comprehensive decarbonization of the economy and the potential for large-scale waste heat utilization, it is imperative to mitigate the investment uncertainties introduced by legislation.

This paper presents a comprehensive analysis of the terminology and structure of the RED III definition of waste heat, focusing on its interaction with other provisions. The aim is to gain a clear understanding of the meaning and scope of this definition. The analysis considers linguistic nuances and technical aspects to identify potential shortcomings, ambiguities, and overreaching elements that could give rise to legal or practical issues in implementing the Directive. Furthermore, the study concentrates on the sectoral objectives of RED III, which necessitate an expansion in the proportion of renewable energy but only partially permit the inclusion of waste heat in these objectives. It analyses the rationale for this approach and its consequences. In order to ascertain the practical relevance of the Directive, conceptual and systematic inconsistencies are identified, and conclusions are drawn. In conclusion, the authors put forth a legal policy proposal for a definition of waste heat that they consider appropriate. For an overview of the key concepts, please refer to Fig. 1.

Section 2 outlines the methodologies employed for the analysis. The findings of the analysis of the waste heat definition are presented in Section 3. The results of the clear separation between waste heat and renewable energy, as well as their ranking in terms of accountability for meeting targets, are presented in Section 4. Section 5 provides a comprehensive legal assessment, including a brief discussion of the

Fig. 1. Overview of the content of the paper. (Source: own figure).

requirements of EED III. The results sections discuss the findings, while the conclusion summarizes the results and derives key statements and recommendations.

2. Methods

In order to gain a precise understanding of the meaning and scope of the definition of waste heat, it is necessary to conduct a comprehensive legal analysis.

Following a comprehensive examination of the defining characteristics of waste heat, a distinction is drawn between waste heat and the terms "renewable energy" (Article 2(1) RED III) and "ambient energy" (Article 2(2) RED III). Subsequently, an analysis and comparison of the relevant waste heat-related provisions of RED III and EED III are conducted with regard to the definitions of "waste heat", "renewable energy", and "ambient energy". Subsequently, we propose an adapted and improved definition of "waste heat". The extent to which the proposed definition fulfills the obligation to transpose directives following Article 288 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU) will be discussed.

In this context, the legal methods of interpretation are applied, considering the specific characteristics of Union law. It is important to adhere to the EU's principle of autonomous interpretation of the Union law, which dictates that it cannot be interpreted based on one or more national legal systems. Subsequently, the literal meaning of the terms utilized in the legal text is ascertained, representing the initial stage of the interpretation process (Bydlinski and Bydlinski, 2023). The Union has a total of 24 official and working languages. In the event of ambiguity or confusion, other language versions may provide a clarifying interpretation. As Huber-Kowald (2023) notes, the treaties are equally binding in all language versions, as set forth in Article 55 of the Treaty on the European Union (TEU) and Article 342 and Article 358 TFEU. In the event of ambiguity or confusion, the wording of a particular language version cannot be preferred in case of doubt, as all language versions are considered to be equally valid and authentic (Huber-Kowald, 2023). The principle of equal multilingualism is observed, but the European Court of Justice generally favors alternative methods of interpretation, such as teleological interpretation (ECJ 15, July 1964). In the context of EU law, teleological interpretation represents the primary method of interpretation. The method of teleological interpretation focuses on the objective meaning and purpose of a legal provision. Accordingly, the European Court of Justice is perpetually directed by the "spirit of the provisions" (ECJ 5, February 1963). The principle of effectiveness, or "effet utile", plays a significant role in the European Court of Justice case law. Consistent with this principle, the interpretation that best enables the provision to have its intended effect must be selected.

In the context of this paper, the aforementioned methods of interpretation are employed to develop a precise definition of waste heat under EU law and elucidate its relationship with the terms "renewable energy" and "ambient energy". The following analysis of the relevant provisions of RED III and the proposal for an adapted definition of waste heat is based on these methodological principles.

3. Definition of waste heat

A closer look at the definition of waste heat reveals that it is a rather intricate and convoluted concept. Clarification and specification are indispensable prerequisites for the efficacious incorporation of the EU Directive into national legislation and advancing investments in waste heat recovery technologies under the Directive.

The following section provides a comprehensive elaboration of the components of the waste heat definition. In order to achieve this, the individual defining characteristics are broken down as follows, based on the wording of RED III.

- a) "unavoidable heat [...] generated as
- b) by-product in
- c) [sectors:] industrial or power generation installations, or in the tertiary sector,
- d) which would be dissipated unused in air or water
- e) without access to a district heating [...],
- f) where a cogeneration process has been used or will be used or where cogeneration is not feasible".

3.1. "Basic" characteristics a-d

Unavoidability: Waste heat is defined as heat that is "unavoidable" heat in a particular process. It is not possible to eliminate or reduce this heat. It should be noted that the term is relative, as technically complex or economically costly measures, as well as the shutting down or non-use of the plant itself, could potentially avoid (parts of) the waste heat. For practical purposes, it is sufficient to refer to various justifications, such as the inability to utilize the heat in the production process for economic, safety, or other reasons, as well as the lack of feasibility to reduce it with reasonable effort (Deutscher Bundestag, 2023). By illustration, industrial processes such as steel production, cooling processes, chemical reactions, and mechanical processes generate heat that cannot be fully integrated into the production process or further utilized. The term "unavoidable" implies that this form of energy loss is an inherent consequence of the process despite the implementation of efficiency measures and technological advancements. In the context of the EED III, the term "unavoidable" can signify that all other feasible energy efficiency measures to reduce waste heat have been fully exhausted (Lyons et al., 2021).

By-product: A by-product is a substance or material produced as an unintended consequence of a primary process. The waste heat generated during industrial, commercial, or energy production processes is classified as a by-product, as its production is not the primary objective. To illustrate, if the objective is to produce a specific commodity, provide a service, or generate electricity, waste heat is an unintended consequence due to technical circumstances, such as friction, prevention of overheating, or limited insulation possibilities. This situation is also reflected in recital 117 of RED II, which characterizes by-products as a non-primary objective of a production process.

In contrast, the heat generated in a combined heat and power (CHP) plant is subject to a different classification (Lyons et al., 2021; European Commission, 2019b). In this context, heat generation is not an unintentional by-product but an integral element of a deliberate combined process in which heat and electricity are produced simultaneously. Following this definition, the heat in question is also called "useful heat" in Annex V of RED III.

Sectoral reference: By the established definition, the generation of waste heat must occur within the context of an industrial plant, an electricity generation plant, or the tertiary sector. This view encompasses many processes, including manufacturing and processing in factories, energy generation in power plants, and services and activities in the tertiary sector, such as data and shopping centers. In the absence of clear assignment to these three sectors, the eligibility of their waste heat is uncertain. The list of waste heat sources is comprehensive, and no sources other than those explicitly mentioned are considered relevant.

The definition of "industrial plant" is particularly challenging to ascertain. It is unclear whether only large-scale industrial operations of a significant scale fall under this term. A legal definition can be found in the Industrial Emissions Directive (2010/75/EU), which defines an "industrial installation" as a stationary technical unit where one or more activities listed in the annexes of the Directive are carried out (Article 3 (3)). Such activities include, for example, energy production, livestock rearing, and the chemical industry. In certain instances, the definition is contingent upon thresholds, such as production capacities, or measures, such as "livestock units", which suggest a specific scale. However, this

definition, which was adopted in the context of combating environmental pollution, is not universally applicable.

Nevertheless, it may be posited that an industrial scale is only attained at a specific magnitude and does not typically encompass small non-industrial agricultural or minor commercial enterprises. Moreover, it is uncertain whether facilities such as waste incineration plants can be considered relevant sources following the definition (Holzleitner and Moser, 2022b). However, the explanatory notes of the Austrian environmental subsidy laws suggest they apply. The implication is that potential sources of waste heat that fall outside the specified sectors may not be considered.

Unused: Waste heat is defined as heat released into the surrounding environment, such as the air or water, without being utilized for a beneficial purpose.

3.2. Access to a district heating system (characteristic e)

In addition to the terms (i) "unavoidable", (ii) "unused", (iii) and "by-product" from (iv) defined sectors, the definition addresses access to a district heating system. In this context, waste heat is a potential resource that may be lost if not fed into a district heating system. The wording implies that contrary to the technical understanding of the term, "waste heat" does not qualify as such without additional structural precautions (i.e., installation of access to the district heating system). In light of the aforementioned considerations, a closer examination of the phrase "[...] which would be dissipated unused in air or water without access to a DHC network [...]" is warranted. This phrase is directed towards the waste heat that would otherwise remain unused without a district heating system and would typically be released into the environment. In other words, this heat would be released unused into the environment (air or water) without district heating infrastructure. The use of the word "would" in this phrase is significant because it introduces a conditional dimension that is also expressed in the linguistic versions of the Directive, such as the Spanish ("que se disiparía") and the German ("abgeleitet würde"). Thus, the wording implies that the waste heat is otherwise considered unused and potentially lost without access to a district heating system.

Thus, the waste heat is regarded as unused following the aforementioned definition, provided that the industrial plant in question has not yet been connected to a district heating system. It can be concluded that waste heat supplied to a district heating network is, by definition, waste heat if the district heating connection has already been installed and is in operation.

This aspect is of particular significance as it indicates that the RED III definition of waste heat is exclusively concerned with waste heat that is or should be delivered to a district heating system. Therefore, it is evident that the aforementioned definition excludes any form of waste heat utilized internally. Therefore, the legal definition is not a comprehensive definition of waste heat, such as heat recovery, in a broader technical understanding that occurs within companies (or between companies if it is not district heating). Consequently, the definition does not apply to other uses of waste heat, such as internal use (see Oluleye et al., 2015) or direct inter-company use (see Moser and Lassacher, 2020). In the latter case, however, there is some ambiguity in the definition of a "district heating system". In particular, it is unclear whether a simple direct pipeline to a neighboring company is sufficient to meet the established criteria for district heating or whether more complex infrastructure is required.

Addressing this issue requires considering the legal definitions provided by European Union legislation. In accordance with Article 2(19) RED III, the term "district heating" is defined as "the distribution of thermal energy in the form of steam or hot water from central or decentralized sources of production through a network to multiple buildings or facilities for the use of space or process heating".

Moreover, in the context of European state aid law, Article 2(124b) of the General Block Exemption Regulation (GBER) (EU) 651/2014

defines a "district heating system" as "heating generation facilities, thermal storage, and a distribution network that includes both a primary (transport) and a secondary network of pipelines comprising both primary and secondary network of pipelines, to supply heating to consumers". It can be inferred from these definitions that not every single pipe or smaller transmission facility is to be considered a system under the Directive. In order to be recognized as a district heating system, a specific size, organization, and structure is required, as well as the capacity to distribute and utilize thermal energy effectively.

3.3. CHP utilization (characteristic f)

The final definitional phrase to consider is "district heating [...] system where a cogeneration process has been used or will be used or where cogeneration is not feasible." For purposes of clarity, the three alternatives are presented separately and distinctly.

- "district heating [...] system where a cogeneration process has been used"
- "district heating [...] system where a cogeneration process will be used"
- "district heating [...] system where a cogeneration process is not feasible".

In particular, the first two variants permit the classification of waste heat as such only if a CHP is or will be employed. Without a CHP, any waste heat that would otherwise meet the aforementioned requirements (characteristics a-e) is not recognized. Without a CHP, using waste heat would be particularly advantageous. In this manner, the definition imposes stipulations on the district heating system in the form of a desired CHP utilization. Consequently, the term "waste heat", as defined, applies only to instances where a district heating system employs a CHP process that will potentially use it or in exceptional cases where this is not feasible. Practically, it is possible to construct district heating systems without CHP, but Red III appears to indicate a preference for systems that incorporate CHP. Therefore, RED III underscores the significance of incorporating CHP systems into the thermal energy infrastructure. The [European Commission \(2024\)](#) reiterates its preference for CHP systems in its communication.

In light of this apparent preference for CHP systems, it is imperative to review this section critically. It is unclear why waste heat should only qualify as such and thus count towards Red III targets if the district heating system uses CHP. Although this stipulation may advance decarbonization and enhanced efficiency, a more comprehensive examination of the broader context, including the energy efficiency and environmental compatibility of waste heat utilization, is essential. The availability of waste heat can be a significant factor in determining the economic non-viability of a CHP system. In cases where the CHP plant is utilized infrequently, for instance, only during peak load periods, the economic justification for its operation may be limited. A simpler heat generation plant, such as a hot water boiler, may offer a more cost-effective alternative. Although CHP plants are designed to retain a maximum exergy level of the energy input, this is not always a technically or economically viable option. In such instances, systems designed exclusively for heat generation (boilers) typically exhibit comparable energy efficiency.

In addition to the aforementioned concerns regarding the suitability of the CHP-related portion of the definition, it is also notable for its lack of coherence. The definition encompasses instances where cogeneration is not feasible. This attribute indicates that the legislator has acknowledged instances where technical limitations, economic constraints, or other factors impede the implementation of a CHP system. Such circumstances may be attributed to the distinctive attributes of the system, including its dimensions or the effects of wear and tear. Furthermore, excessive investment costs may also be a contributing factor. For instance, if the costs significantly exceed the anticipated benefits or cost

reductions, it may be deemed economically infeasible.

Furthermore, site constraints and the availability and type of fuel required to operate a CHP system may also be relevant considerations. Nevertheless, it is unclear what the legal consequences would be if CHP were technically feasible but not implemented, a provision where a variant could be definitively argued. However, if the text of the definition is implemented literally, it must be assumed that, in this case, the definition is not met, and therefore, there is no waste heat in the sense of the definition.

A definition of waste heat contingent upon the utilization or potential utilization of a CHP system may result in the inadvertent exclusion of efficient and climate-friendly alternatives that do not employ cogeneration. Such a situation could dissuade companies from investing in waste heat infrastructure.

3.4. Discussion

From a technical standpoint, the three characteristics of being unavoidable, unused (in this case, for internal use), and an unintended by-product provide an excellent description of waste heat. Furthermore, the additional stipulation that it would be discharged unused due to a lack of internal usability, feed-in, or other external use enhances the explanatory quality of the waste heat definition. These characteristics align with the prevailing technical understanding of waste heat.

In practice, however, there is often no further potential for utilizing the waste heat. If the heat is readily recoverable, or if it must be recovered, for instance, due to regulatory requirements, then electricity generation via steam turbines or ORC processes represents a viable option. Electricity generation (and thus producing a high-exergy, high-cost energy carrier) is paramount at exceedingly high temperatures and pressures. Nevertheless, it is challenging to attain electrical efficiencies of 25% or above when residual waste heat levels are in the range of 300 °C and below (Markides, 2013; Pethurajan et al., 2018; Stainchaouer et al., 2024; Wesselak et al., 2017). Therefore, electricity generation at this temperature level is a relatively last resort option and should only be considered after all other potential uses of waste heat have been exhausted. Using waste heat as process heat in external plants or district heating allows for up to 100% efficiency. The fact that electricity generation is a last resort should not preclude its acceptance as waste heat for more efficient uses. In other words, waste heat that could be used elsewhere with higher efficiency should not fail the "unused" criterion because it is already electrified with low efficiency. This issue is complex and nuanced, but it is crucial to clarify the parameters to ensure overall energy efficiency.

The list of sectors is exclusive, and while it likely encompasses the most significant areas, it may omit potential sources of waste heat. It is reasonable to prioritize the sectors with the greatest potential, as the cost-benefit analysis is relatively straightforward, and there are likely to be specific contacts (energy officers) within the companies. However, Moser and Lassacher (2020) demonstrate that there is no minimum size for waste heat utilization in district heating networks if the framework conditions (profiles, distances, and recovery possibilities) are suitable. The feed-in from sources smaller than one MW is recorded.

The aforementioned features (district heating system and CHP utilization) represent supplementary specifications for waste heat utilization, where there is a discrepancy between the definition and the general technical understanding. As set forth in RED III, the definition of waste heat applies solely to waste heat associated with utilizing a district heating system. The definition of waste heat does not apply to other, primarily internal potentials and realizations of heat recovery. This limitation is regrettable, as a comprehensive and well-defined legal definition could provide legal certainty in other areas, including heat reuse within a single company (see Lyons et al., 2021) or heat exchange between two companies.

The lack of clarity regarding the use of CHP can give rise to uncertainty regarding the accountability of waste heat. If projects are

implemented but not recognized, this would effectively constitute a heat purchase, including waste heat, which would fail to contribute to RED III targets and ultimately require replacement over time. These disadvantages stem from an opaque preference for CHP plants, as evidenced by the definition of waste heat as a discrete component of the district heating network. Notably, "waste heat" is recognized when a cogeneration plant is already integrated into the district heating network. Conversely, one would anticipate that CHP would be employed mainly when a district heating network is not supplied with sustainable energy, such as waste heat. The heat generated by CHP is intentionally produced, and the primary energy input (and CO₂ emissions) must be allocated (Buchenau et al., 2023). It is recommended that CHP be promoted in conjunction with thermal energy storage, enabling electricity-oriented operation (see Lepiksaar et al., 2021), particularly in the absence of waste heat.

4. Differentiation of waste heat from "renewable energy"

RED III defines renewable energy as "energy from renewable non-fossil sources, namely wind, solar (solar thermal and solar photovoltaic) and geothermal energy, osmotic energy, ambient energy, tide, wave and other ocean energy, hydropower, biomass, landfill gas, sewage treatment plant gas, and biogas". It should be noted that this list is considered exhaustive; therefore, any other forms of energy production are not considered renewable. Concurrently, the RED III definition of waste heat does not consider the original energy source, whether renewable energy, fossil fuels, or a combination of fuels, the process from which the waste heat originates.

This section elucidates how RED III differentiates waste heat and renewable energy and presents the chosen approach (subsection 4.1). Subsection 4.2 then elucidates how waste heat is ranked relative to renewables for its eligibility for RED III targets. Subsection 4.3 presents a rationale for this ranking and its future configuration, as it also applies to waste heat from processes fueled by renewable energy sources. Subsection 4.4 examines the practical confusion that arises when the definitions of waste heat and renewable energy are applied to situations where the waste heat has left the boundaries of the industrial site and becomes ambient heat.

4.1. Distinction of sources of district heating heat supply

The primary energy input for district heating, or for the actors (e.g., industry) where the waste heat originates, is either renewable or non-renewable energy. The latter category also encompasses other technologies, such as nuclear, but primarily refers to fossil energy in the heating sector. RED III differentiates between energy utilized as a primary input and an unavoidable unused by-product.

Accordingly, the heat in heating networks can be derived from four distinct sources, as illustrated in Fig. 2. The upper right box illustrates the scenario where fossil primary energy supplies district heating. In general, this is the prevailing situation in Europe. The upper left box depicts the optimal renewable energy supply, as outlined in RED III. However, it is essential to acknowledge that RED III also acknowledges and encourages waste heat utilization, albeit with a comparatively lesser emphasis (see 4.2). The boxes below illustrate the waste heat generated by the primary processes listed in the upper boxes.

While waste heat exemplifies the efficiency-first principle by utilizing existing energy flows, it is important to recognize that locally available renewable sources, such as geothermal and solar thermal energy, also face challenges of underutilization. If these sources remain untapped, they may also be regarded as wasted resources. Accordingly, prioritizing waste heat and renewables must be contextual, balancing immediacy, cost-effectiveness, and integration feasibility. For instance, waste heat may be given precedence in industrial zones with preexisting infrastructure, whereas geothermal or solar thermal solutions may be more appropriate in rural or greenfield developments. This approach is

Fig. 2. Four possible sources of district heating heat supply. (Source: Energieinstitut an der JKU Linz).

consistent with maximizing the utilization of available resources for decarbonization.

In RED III, the legislator opted not to differentiate based on primary energy input when defining waste heat (vertical separation). The rationale behind this decision probably is that waste heat is an unavoidable by-product that would otherwise be lost. Consequently, the link to the primary input is removed. It can be posited that a novel energy source is generated, albeit not renewable, yet comparatively low in emissions. Waste heat can be derived from fossil and renewable processes (horizontal separation).

Consequently, a combination of fossil and renewable energy inputs can be used to obtain the same quality of waste heat, as is often the case, for instance, in the pulp and paper industry, where biomass and natural gas are employed. In light of this line of reasoning, it becomes evident that the terminology "fossil (or renewable) waste heat" is not an accurate representation and should be replaced with "waste heat from fossil (or renewable) fueled/powering processes". RED III emphasizes the promotion of renewable energy sources, whereas the Energy Efficiency Directive (EED) prioritizes improving energy efficiency, encompassing

waste heat utilization. It is paramount to highlight the role of waste heat in the context of RED III, as it complements the renewable energy targets and promotes a more comprehensive approach to sustainability. Furthermore, both directives must establish a coherent and aligned legal framework to ensure effective implementation, thereby maximizing the efficiency and sustainability of energy systems in the EU.

The inclusion of waste heat recovery regulations within RED III, which aims to increase the share of renewable energy in the energy mix, raises questions regarding the suitability of this legislative context. Although waste heat significantly contributes to decarbonization by reducing overall energy demand and emissions, it is not classified as a renewable energy source under RED III. This policy introduces the possibility of a discrepancy between the Directive's primary objectives and the role of waste heat.

An alternative approach could entail anchoring waste heat recovery regulations more prominently within the EED, which targets energy savings and efficiency improvements. The EED's emphasis on reducing energy consumption is more closely aligned with the nature of waste heat as an efficiency measure. An alternative approach would be to

adopt a dual-framework strategy, whereby RED III continues to integrate waste heat into renewable energy targets as a supplementary measure while the EED provides a dedicated platform for promoting its recovery and utilization. This approach would guarantee that waste heat is utilized effectively without compromising the emphasis on renewables within RED III. Waste heat can be recognized as a new energy source, provided that the conditions of unavailability and being an unused by-product are met. In such cases, the aforementioned differentiation method should be employed (i.e., a horizontal separation, according to Fig. 2). The waste heat generated by industrial processes predominantly fueled by fossil fuels should not be discarded (see below). Moreover, it can be reasonably assumed that converting fossil-fuel-powered processes to renewable-fueled processes will be necessary to align with the Union's Green Deal objectives.

From an economic standpoint, in alignment with the Green Deal Directives about green financing, it is also a secondary condition that the revenues from selling waste heat should not result in a lock-in effect that is more pronounced than the transition requirement. From a regulatory perspective, it is reasonable to conclude that unavoidable and otherwise unused heat is treated similarly regardless of its original energy source. Fossil fuels meet most industrial process heat demand; thus, waste heat is predominantly derived from fossil fuel-fired processes. This waste heat also represents an existing and otherwise lost resource, regardless of its original form. It thus appears reasonable to conclude that equal treatment may be appropriate, at least for the time being, given that decarbonization measures will inevitably affect these fossil-fueled processes.

Consequently, their waste heat will ultimately derive from non-fossil processes. The advantages of accepting waste heat from fossil processes would be that these waste heat sources would be connected to the district heating system at the time of the transition, thereby ensuring that the waste heat generated up to that point would not remain unused. During the industrial company's transition, an existing connection to district heating will result in a proactive consideration of the recovery of waste heat from the climate-neutral process for district heating.

In a climate-neutral, sustainable energy system (cf. Böhm et al., 2021), energy use should be energy and exergy efficient. It can be concluded that the primary objective should be to achieve the lower left box of the matrix for the provision of space and water heating when high-exergy renewables are used as the primary energy input, for example, electricity, renewable gases, or biomass. Similarly, low-exergy renewables, such as geothermal, should also be preferred due to their local availability and potential for utilization.

4.2. Accountability restrictions for waste heat

The primary objective of the Renewable Energy Directive (RED III) is to augment the proportion of renewable energy in the energy mix. Accordingly, RED III establishes sector-specific targets. As previously stated, waste heat is not classified as a renewable energy source under the provisions of RED III. In contrast, partial eligibility is followed. RED III permits Member States to incorporate waste heat to a specified percentage into their national energy and climate plans. The sectoral targets are presented in Table 1 below.

The individual targets and the accountability of waste heat demonstrate a clear preference for renewables over waste heat. In instances where Member States utilize waste heat to fulfill their established targets, the ambition associated with the target is increased by 50%; 1.5 percentage points of waste heat equals 1 percentage point of renewables. The sectoral target for district heating, which does not increase the level of ambition when waste heat is used, represents an exception that considers this sector's technical and economic specifics positively.

Nevertheless, the outcomes can be synthesized as follows.

- Waste heat is accepted as a clean energy source that merits recognition alongside renewable energies.

Table 1
Sectoral targets, waste heat eligibility, and findings.

Sector	Article	RES Target	Waste Heat Eligibility	Target increment due to consideration of waste heat
Building sector	15a	49% of final energy consumption by 2030. Member States define individual targets	Up to a limit of 20%	The reference value for the national share is increased by half of the percentage of waste heat used that is counted towards this share
Industrial sector	22a	The indicative target is to take the form of an annual indicative value of 1,6 percentage points per annum for the periods 2021–2025 and 2026–2030 as a calculated average	Up to a limit of 0,4 percentage points	The average annual increase will be increased by half the percentage points of the waste heat taken into account
The heating and cooling sector	23	At least 0,8 percentage points/a (2021–2025) and 1,1 percentage points/a (2026–2030)	Up to a limit of 0,4 percentage points	The average annual increase is increased by half of the percentage points of waste heat and cooling consumed
District heating sector	24	2,2 percentage points/an increase in the share of renewable energies compared to 2020 is standardized	Waste heat is regarded as an equivalent of renewable energy	

- However, waste heat is of secondary importance compared to renewable energies.

Thus, there is an element of uncertainty as to whether the position of waste heat could deteriorate further in future iterations of the Directive.

Waste heat plays a distinctive role in decarbonization, utilizing energy that would otherwise be lost, thereby reducing the necessity for supplementary primary energy input, whether derived from fossil or renewable sources. Although RED III and EED III acknowledge the potential of waste heat as a contributor to decarbonization, their emphasis remains on renewable energy as the primary focus. Nevertheless, there are instances when prioritizing waste heat is more pressing and efficacious, particularly when it can swiftly supplant fossil fuel utilization or augment the efficiency of existing systems. For example, integrating waste heat into district heating systems is consistent with the EU's Energy Efficiency First principle, as it optimizes the utilization of existing energy flows and infrastructure.

Moreover, the temporal and spatial immediacy of waste heat utilization, which often necessitates fewer investments than the deployment of new renewable energy systems, makes it a more expedient decarbonization measure in some contexts. This opportunity is particularly relevant in urban areas with existing industrial or commercial waste heat sources, where district heating networks can be expanded to tap into these resources without delay. Such measures reduce greenhouse gas emissions and facilitate a more gradual transition towards a sustainable energy system. Legislators could reinforce the prioritization of waste heat by explicitly associating its utilization with immediate decarbonization objectives in the heating and industrial sectors.

4.3. "Renewable" waste heat?

As previously stated, waste heat can emanate from fossil and renewable processes, and the RED III system does not differentiate between the two. As stated in section 4.1, this is also justifiable and understandable from a legal policy perspective. Nevertheless, as renewable energy sources expand, it may be prudent to re-examine the rationale behind the current approach of not making a distinction. The optimal use of waste heat from processes operated with renewable energy would result in reduced emissions, enhanced energy efficiency, and improved energy adequacy. By meeting the heat demand at an appropriate temperature level, the efficient use of this heat would lead to conserving renewable resources, reducing economic scarcity and improving market prices. It appears incongruous to restrict this optimal scenario of utilizing waste heat from processes driven by renewable energy sources by establishing a maximum percentage of target accountability. In light of the aforementioned considerations, it may be advisable to consider including waste heat from processes fueled by renewable energy sources as "green waste heat" in the definition of renewable energy sources. This approach would ensure full eligibility for the expansion targets of RED III while allowing for partial accounting of non-"green waste heat".

4.4. Waste heat may constitute a component of ambient energy

In the comprehensive enumeration of renewable energy sources, waste heat is not included and thus is not classified as such. It is imperative to acknowledge the interplay between waste heat and ambient energy. Ambient energy is defined in RED III as "naturally occurring thermal energy and energy accumulated in the environment with constrained boundaries, which can be stored in the ambient air, excluding in exhaust air, or surface or sewage water". Although the term "ambient energy" is typically used to describe naturally occurring thermal energy, such as that found in air and groundwater, it can also be applied to waste heat from industrial processes discharged into and contained in surface water, which is covered by the definition. This paradoxical result would mean that the heat recovered from the wastewater system would no longer be considered waste but ambient heat and, thus, renewable. However, this interpretation is untenable in the RED III system context because it obscures the fundamental distinction between renewable energy sources and the efficient use of waste heat. It is only possible to count waste heat towards renewable energy targets in the system of sectoral targets to a limited extent. Such a classification would be nonsensical and contradictory to the values of RED III, as it would give heat that is first discharged into water and then recover a superior position in terms of target achievement. RED III does not intend to reclassify waste heat indirectly, nor should it provide an incentive to obtain a different status by accepting high-efficiency losses. From the legislator's perspective, it is evident that a clear delineation must be established, which in this case was defined by the boundary between the industrial facility and the public sewer system.

An Austrian applied research project (Industrial Microgrids, research grant number FFG 868708), in which the authors participated, investigated the potential for utilizing the waste heat from the wastewater of a large laundry facility to provide heating for a neighboring business. The business is situated in an area not serviced by a district heating network. The waste heat would have been collected a few meters before the wastewater entered the public sewer, recovered using a heat pump, and then delivered to the neighboring business. The wastewater would still have been discharged into the public sewer at a slightly lower temperature. The "waste heat" from the laundry company would not have qualified as such, as the definition requires a district heating network (not only a direct line). If the heat were extracted a few meters later, for instance, by utilizing heat exchangers in the sewer system, the heat would qualify as renewable energy. The wastewater would cool down due to mixing with other wastewater, necessitating more energy input from the heat pump for upcycling. The slight discrepancy in the

positioning of the heat recovery system results in a reduction in the system's energy efficiency, but in the absence of access to a district heating system and subsequent discharge of the waste heat into a sewer, the system would meet the criteria for classification as renewable energy. This example demonstrates the inconsistency and lack of coherence in the definition. In this instance, the waste heat in question could not be included in the RED III accounting system due to a lack of access to a district heating system. However, this would not preclude its potential classification as renewable energy in the form of ambient heat in wastewater.

5. Waste heat in the Energy Efficiency Directive

In addition to the provisions of RED III, the EED III also contains regulations concerning waste heat. Article 26 defines an "efficient district heating system". Until the end of 2027, networks will comply with the definition if they utilize at least 50% renewable energy, 50% waste heat, 75% CHP heat, or 50% of a combination of these forms of energy or heat. The requirements will increase gradually (2028, 2035, 2040, 2045) until 2050, when a network may only use renewable energy, waste heat, or a combination of both. The increases will occur in 2028, 2035, 2040, and 2045. The EED prioritizes waste heat utilization higher than RED III.

According to Recital 105 of the Energy Efficiency Directive, the definition of waste heat in RED III is applicable. The significance of the RED III definition of waste heat gives rise to interactions between the two pieces of legislation. The two definitions consistently require the integration of waste heat into a district heating system. An efficient district heating system is characterized by, among other things, the use of waste heat. However, the definition of waste heat in RED III stipulates that any integration of waste heat into an efficient district heating system necessitates the use of combined heat and power (CHP), thereby rendering the utilization of waste heat in an efficient district heating system contingent upon the concurrent operation of CHP. It should be noted that the aforementioned definition excludes the case in which cogeneration is not possible. It can be surmised that including CHP is not feasible in meeting the requirements; however, this logic is incongruent with the legislator's intentions.

Additionally, the Energy Efficiency Directive contains stipulations congruent with the definition of waste heat outlined in RED III. Following Article 26(7), companies must assess the potential for utilizing waste heat when developing new installations or substantially refurbishing existing ones. The primary option is the internal reuse of waste heat. The RED III definition does not allow for the internal reuse of waste heat and requires a connection to a district heating system with a combined heat and power (CHP) unit, which is not applicable in this situation. The EU legislator is unaware of the constraints imposed by linking the EED III provisions to the RED III waste heat definition.

6. Conclusions

We draw five principal conclusions in light of the findings presented in the preceding sections.

6.1. The wording used in the definition

The analysis concludes that the definition of waste heat in RED III is complex, unclear, and subject to complex and time-consuming legal interpretation steps. The definition does not align with the prevailing technical understanding of waste heat.

- The definition is deliberately designed for the context of district heating. Nevertheless, our analysis has demonstrated that other sections of RED III and EED III refer to the definition of waste heat despite the absence of direct relevance to district heating. A more general, distinct definition of waste heat is absent from the EU

legislation, including the EED III and other pertinent EU legislation. Thus, the definition of waste heat in RED III should be improved by deleting its final section on district heating and cogeneration. It is recommended that the stipulation about district heating systems with CHP plants be eliminated.

- The definition’s exhaustive list of sources (industry, power generation, and the tertiary sector) leaves unaddressed many potential sources of waste heat, thus limiting the scope of its applicability. It thus follows that it should be open to all sectors. It would be more appropriate to list the sources of waste heat (industry, electricity generation, and the tertiary sector) demonstrative.

The two issues are addressed in a concrete proposal derived in Table 2. The proposal deliberately employs only those parts of the RED III definition that apply system-, technology-, and design-agnostic terminologies. The specific statements on district heating and cogeneration have been removed. At the same time, the proposal retains the familiar wording of RED III because its initial sections are correctly applied and make it straightforward to modify during a revision of the Directive.

Article 288 of the TFEU outlines that directives are legally binding regarding their objectives to be achieved by the Member States (Vcelouch, 2023). Nevertheless, it is at the discretion of the national legislator to determine the specific form and means of implementation of the directive. When a Member State is implementing a directive at the national level, it is incumbent upon them to ensure that the objectives set out in the directive are fully achieved and that no compromises are made. In practice, Member States are occasionally confronted with highly detailed directives that leave only limited flexibility for transposition at the national level (Vcelouch, 2023). To illustrate, the Austrian legislator has enacted the Renewables Extension Act, which transposes the RED III definition into national law with identical wording. Regarding the definition of waste heat proposed here, it should be noted that although it is possible to make the definition more precise, it would not be permissible to reduce the meaning and scope of the definition set forth in the Directive. Consequently, the recommendation is directed towards the European legislator, given that enhancements at the national level are only feasible or permissible to a restricted degree.

A significant element of the proposed definition is its deliberate avoidance of technical categorizations, which guarantees the inclusion of all forms of waste heat, irrespective of their provenance or distinctive attributes. This approach is particularly pertinent for traditionally overlooked sectors, such as agriculture or small-scale enterprises. By broadening the scope in this manner, the definition enhances its practical applicability and facilitates the integration of waste heat into existing and future energy systems. Moreover, the proposed definition is distinguished by its practical orientation, as evidenced by the decoupling of waste heat assessment from the CHP connectivity requirement. This modification reduces the obstacles faced by companies seeking to leverage their waste heat potential yet lacking the requisite economic or technical viability to implement a CHP system. Removing this dependency enables the definition to support a more expansive range of waste heat recovery projects, thereby aligning to maximize energy

Table 2
Proposal for an improved definition of waste heat.

Definition, according to RED III	Proposed new definition
“waste heat [...]: unavoidable heat [...] generated as by-product in industrial or power generation installations, or in the tertiary sector, which would be dissipated unused in air or water without access to a district heating [...], where a cogeneration process has been used or will be used or where cogeneration is not feasible”	“waste heat [...]: unavoidable heat [...] generated as by-product, in particular in industrial or power generation installations, or in the tertiary sector, which would be dissipated unused in air or water”

efficiency.

The proposed definition enhances the practical usability of waste heat potentials by ensuring openness to diverse waste heat sources and removing dependencies on specific technical requirements, such as CHP connectivity. This approach facilitates the broader integration of waste heat into energy systems, thereby ensuring the effective utilization of previously untapped resources, particularly in underrepresented sectors.

The proposed definition essentially adopts the wording of the existing RED III definition and attempts to enhance it by incorporating additional elements and omitting others. The objective is to arrive at a definition that can be readily incorporated into the legal framework, given its resemblance to the extant situation. This recommendation addresses a short-term improvement, whereas the placement of waste heat (which is a topic related to efficiency) in RED III raises the question of whether it may not need to be assigned to another directive (EED III) in the long term (see 6.5). It is important to note that the proposed definition has two limitations. Firstly, it does not account for each case’s specific technical and techno-economic circumstances. Secondly, it does not differentiate itself from the multitude of existing definitions in the scientific literature, which are often implicit and rarely explicit (for a discussion of these definitions, see [Berntsson and Åsblad, 2015](#)).

6.2. Exclusive applicability to district heating networks

In accordance with the established criteria, the present definition of waste heat applies *solely* to instances where the heat in question is or will be utilized for district heating networks. The definition does not extend to other applications, such as internal reuse or reuse by entities other than district heating companies. It is of the utmost importance that the EED III and those parts of RED III that de facto refer to the internal use of waste heat do not refer to this definition because the definition of waste heat in RED III has indirect effects. For example, the General Block Exemption Regulation (GBER), in turn, affects national funding for efficient technologies.

6.3. Uncertainty about waste heat from green processes

One optimal scenario, and implicitly the future scenario envisioned for high-exergy renewables, is to utilize renewables in industrial processes and to employ their unavoidable waste heat for heating purposes, namely in a cascaded manner. However, it should be noted that waste heat from processes powered by renewable energy is also waste heat and would not be treated equally in the current version of RED III. It is possible to include waste heat from purely green primary energy sources in the definition of renewables while ensuring that the waste heat from non-renewable operated processes is not disadvantaged. One potential solution is incorporating waste heat from initially green processes into the RED III definition of renewable energy.

Moreover, it is essential to elucidate the interrelationship between renewable ambient heat and waste heat.

6.4. Do not prevent the connection of waste heat

Utilizing waste heat in district heating does not result in a significant lock-in effect for fossil technologies. It is of significant importance to integrate industrial waste heat as soon as feasible. Firstly, the unavoidable waste heat from fossil processes should not be left unused; secondly, industrial companies already connected to district heating will be more inclined to consider the potential of waste heat feed-in when planning their green transition.

This consideration is pertinent, given that it can be assumed that in the short to medium term, there will still be fossil processes whose waste heat should be utilized to circumvent the direct use of thermal energy within a sustainable and efficient energy system. Therefore, reusing unavoidable waste heat increases overall energy efficiency directly ([Holzleitner and Moser, 2022b](#)). It is evident that unavoidable waste

heat frequently occurs at relatively low temperatures, e.g., less than 100 °C, and thus stands to benefit from reductions in district heating network temperature (as proposed by Pakere et al., 2023). Furthermore, integrating industrial process heat and district heating planning (as recommended by Knöttner et al., 2022) could prove advantageous.

6.5. Clarity regarding the status of waste heat

The notion that renewable energy has minimal CO₂ emissions is contingent upon including supply chains in the assessment (for a detailed examination of this, see the standard values presented in Tol-eikyte et al., 2023). In district heating, Red III equates waste heat with renewable energy. Consequently, waste heat is accorded the same status as renewable energy.

By broadening the definition to encompass non-traditional sectors and decoupling it from specific technological prerequisites such as CHP, the framework can more closely align with legislative priorities that aim to accelerate the deployment of energy efficiency measures. In order to facilitate this, it is recommended that waste heat utilization is explicitly prioritized in short- and medium-term policy goals, particularly as a complement to renewable energy in achieving decarbonization objectives.

In order to enhance the coherence of waste heat recovery regulations, it is recommended that a dual-framework approach be explored. Although RED III can continue to acknowledge waste heat as a supplementary measure to renewables, the EED could establish a dedicated platform to facilitate the broader integration of waste heat recovery across all sectors. Such an approach would result in a more precise alignment between the legislative treatment of waste heat and its role in improving energy efficiency and achieving decarbonization goals.

It is evident that waste heat is not classified as a renewable energy source. Despite being treated equally in the assessment, the designation of waste heat remains unclear. As Lyons et al. (2021, p. 42) noted, the sale of waste heat as a green product is challenging, particularly when the related processes are fossil-fueled. In light of the numerous discussions on terminology (e.g., climate-neutral, carbon-neutral, and net-zero) that have also emerged in related scientific fields (see, for instance, Olfe-Kräutlein et al., 2022; Zeilerbauer et al., 2024, on carbon circularity), it is challenging to propose a common umbrella term. However, we propose introducing a new term, e.g. "low-CO₂" heat sources, encompassing both renewable and waste heat. This concept would clarify that waste heat is not associated with a significant emission burden.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Marie-Theres Holzleitner-Senck: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Simon Moser:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Supervision, Project administration, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Michael Denk:** Writing – original draft, Investigation, Formal analysis.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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